

INTERNET USAGE AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS
FOR- LEARNING TAMIL

K.JAGADEESH¹ DR. A. SUBRAMANIAN²

1. Ph.D. (UGC-RGNF-JRF) Research Scholar, Department of Education,
University of Madras, Chennai-600 005. Tamil Nadu, India.

2. Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Madras,
Chennai- 600 005. Tamil Nadu, India.

“The Internet’s next big thing might be going to school”

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Abstract

The research study focused on Internet usage among higher secondary students for learning Tamil. Descriptive survey method was employed to collect the data through questionnaire by adopting stratified random sampling technique. The questionnaire was constructed and validated by the researchers. The sample size of this study comprises 500 higher secondary school students, among them 276 were boys and 224 were girls studying in various districts of Tamil Nadu. The objectives of the study is to assess the level of internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students and to find the Internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students based on Gender, Medium of Instruction, Locality of the School, Type of School and School Management. The results indicate that, the internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students is low. It is also found that there is a significant difference in Internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students with respect to Gender, Locality of the School, Type of School, School Management and there is no significant difference in Internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students with respect to Medium of Instruction.

Key Words: Internet Usage, Virtual Classroom, m- Learning, Online Conferencing.

Introduction

Technology has entered the portals of our life in a big way and will continue to stay for a long time to come in modified packages. Since technology is impacting each and every domain of life, education has largely been influenced by technology. Use of computers and advanced form of ICT in the field of education has a tremendous scope in improving the products and processes of education. ICT can help teachers, learners, researchers, and educational planners to get access to a valuable treasure of knowledge, skill and application for improving their own tasks. Virtual classrooms, e-learning and m-learning are the latest concepts and trends that are emerging in the educational horizon of our country.

Internet is a worldwide collection of computer networks connecting academic, governmental, commercial and organizational sites. Internet service include direct communication (e-mail, Chat), online conferencing, Internet News, e- mail discussion lists, distributed information resources (worldwide web) remote login and file transfer protocol and many other valuable tools and resources. Through internet, students, parents and teachers with limited resources can have access to an extensive array of information sources.

E-learning is defined as an instruction delivered on a computer by use of CDROM, Internet or intranet with content relevant to the learning objectives, use instructional methods to help learning, use words in the form of audio, print and graphics such as illustrations, photos, animation or video.

Review of Literature

Researchers have been conducted on assessment of ICT literacy among high school students (Uma Maheswari et al 2010), utilization of online programs by teachers in teaching-learning process at secondary level (Paul Devanesan, Selvan, 2012). Research studies were conducted on knowledge, attitude and internet usage among dental students (Pramod K.Jali etl2014), usage of internet resources among engineering students (Chinnasamy et al 2014). Attitude towards computer and internet usage among

Postgraduate students in Malaysia (Nabeel Abedalaziz etal 2013). Only few studies have been conducted on utilization of webresouces for language teaching and learning especially for tamil at the higher secondary level. Hence the present study focuses on internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students.

Need for the Study

In the present day scenario involvement and interest of higher secondary students in learning Tamil is found to be decreasing. In order to create awareness about the availability of resources and facilities in the web sites for learning Tamil and enable them to search for the job opportunities available if they learn Tamil, to motivate them to use web sources for learning Tamil, the present study is undertaken.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the level of internet usage for learning Tamil among higher secondary students.
- To find out the extent of internet usage for learning Tamil among higher secondary students with respect to the following dimension:
 - Accessibility
 - Interest
 - Awareness
 - Tamil content availability in the websites
 - Utilization of web sources for teaching Tamil by teachers
- To find out whether any significant difference exist in the internet usage by higher secondary students for learning Tamil with respect to the following sub groups:
 - Gender
 - Medium of instruction
 - Locality of the school
 - Type of school (Boys, Girls, Co-ed)
 - Management (Govt, Aided, Corporation)

Method and Procedure

Descriptive survey method is adopted for this study.

Pilot Study

In order to validate and to find out the appropriateness of the tool constructed by the researchers pilot study was conducted on a sample size of 50. The final tool was constructed after removing 20 statements (based on Item total correlation value)

Tool used

Internet usage questionnaire under five dimensions (Accessibility, Interest, Awareness, Tamil content availability and Utilization of web sources for teaching Tamil by teachers)(with 9,7,9,10,11 statements respectively) on a four point scale (Always, At-times, Rarely, Never), constructed and validated by the researchers was used in this study. Reliability of the tool is found to be (split-half method) 0.9.

Sample

Stratified random sampling technique was used. Sample for this study consist of 500 higher secondary students (both boys & girls) of XI & XII standards studying in Government, Government Aided and Corporation schools from seven districts of Tamil Nadu (Chennai, Thiruvallur, Kancheepuram, Vellore, Krishnagiri, Dharmapuri, and Thanjavur). Sample distribution is given in Table 1.

Table – 1
Sample Distribution

Gender		Medium		Locality Of The School		School Management			Type Of School		
Boys	Girls	Tamil	English	Rural	Urban	Govt	Govt.Aided	Corporation	Boys	Girls	Co-Ed
276	224	410	90	255	245	258	174	68	117	160	223
500		500		500		500			500		

Analysis and Discussion

Table - 2

Level of Internet usage for learning Tamil

Variable	Level	N	Percentage (%)
Internet Usage	High	11	2.2
	Moderate	187	37.4
	Low	302	60.4

Results of the above table-2 shows that 60.4%, 37.4%, 2.2% of the sample have low, moderate, high level of internet usage for learning tamil respectively.

Figure - 1

Table - 3
Descriptive Statistics

Dimensions	N	Mean	S.D
Accessibility	500	20.3(22.5)	5.54
Interest	500	18.1(17.5)	4.85
Awareness	500	23.2(22.5)	6.24
Tamil content availability	500	24.9 (25)	6.21
Teaching	500	25.8(27.5)	7.5

Results of the above table-3 shows that mean score values for all the dimensions are almost nearer to the mid-values of a particular dimension. (Mid values given in parenthesis)

Table - 4

The Mean, S.D, 't' value on Internet Usage with Respect following sub groups

Sub variable	Group	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value	Level of significance
Gender	Boys	276	117.08	25.35	4.73	0.01
	Girls	224	106.93	21.89		
Medium	Tamil	410	112.52	24.36	0.02	Not Significant
	English	90	112.58	24.52		
Locality of the school	Urban	245	116.84	25.6	3.931	0.01
	Rural	255	108.39	22.4		

A result of Table -4 shows that there is significant difference between boys and girls, rural and urban students in their internet usage for learning tamil. Based on the mean score boys have more internet usage knowledge for learning tamil compare to girls and Urban students also have more internet usage knowledge for learning tamil compare to rural students.

The boys often go to browsing centers with their peer group for playing games in internet. So, boys have more internet usage knowledge compared to girls. Urban students are easily accessible towards ICT technology. Whereas, rural students lack instructional infrastructure related to ICT. Most of the urban students have internet connections at home. Rural students due to their socio economic status lack in internet at home. Hence, the urban students have more internet usage compare to counterparts.

Table - 5

The ‘F’ value on Internet Usage with Respect following sub groups

Sub variable	Group		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	L.O.S	GROUP DIFFER
Type school of	Boys	Between Groups	21261.8	2	10630.9	19.205	0.01	B&G B&CO-ED CO-ED&G
	Girls							
	Co-Ed	Within Groups	275117	497	553.555			
		Total	296379	499				
School Management	Govt Aided	Between Groups	7144.44	2	3572.22	6.138	0.01	G&A
	Private							
			Total	296379	499			

Results of Table 5 shows that students from government, government aided and corporation schools as well from boys, girls, co-education schools differ in their internet usage. In Type of school, based on mean scores, Boys have more internet usage knowledge for learning tamil compared to their counter parts. Boys have more interest towards computer technology and browsing the new information through the computer. So, boys’ school students have more internet usage knowledge compared to their counterparts.

In School Management, based on mean scores, Aided school students have more internet usage knowledge for learning tamil compare to other counter parts. Aided schools motivate and encourage the students in teaching and learning through ICT. Therefore

aided school students have more internet usage knowledge compared to their counterparts.

Table 6

Descriptive statistics for each subscale with dimensions (n=500)							
			Accessibility	Interest	Awareness	Tamil content Availability	Teaching
Gender	Male	Mean	21.74	18.17	24.67	25.92	26.59
		S.D	5.5	5.01	6.1	6.54	7.85
	Female	Mean	18.62	18.06	21.48	23.85	24.92
		S.D	5.09	4.65	5.97	5.59	6.95
Medium	Tamil	Mean	20.33	18.15	23.18	24.95	25.92
		S.D	5.45	4.84	6.31	6.15	7.54
	English	Mean	20.4	17.99	23.52	25.19	25.48
		S.D	5.93	4.9	5.93	6.51	7.34
Locality of the school	Urban	Mean	21.18	18.62	24.99	26.2	25.85
		S.D	5.8	4.79	6.19	6.57	8.15
	Rural	Mean	19.54	17.64	21.56	23.83	25.83
		S.D	5.09	4.87	5.82	5.62	6.84
Type of the school	Boys	Mean	22.51	18.68	25.19	26.44	28.7
		S.D	4.7	4.53	5.39	5.54	6.39
	Girls	Mean	17.95	17.92	20.27	23.12	24.84
		S.D	4.89	4.67	5.54	5.45	6.56
	Co-Ed	Mean	20.92	17.96	24.35	25.57	25.06
		S.D	5.77	5.13	6.39	6.74	8.29
School Management	Government	Mean	19.73	17.95	21.93	24.19	25.55
		S.D	5.46	5.15	6.41	6.35	7.01
	Aided	Mean	21.3	18.34	24.53	25.87	27.56
		S.D	5.45	4.35	5.58	5.53	7.16
	Corporation	Mean	20.22	18.16	24.91	25.76	22.57
		S.D	5.77	4.92	6.19	6.95	8.91

Results of Table 6 shows that the mean scores of internet usage for the dimensions

accessibility to internet and awareness are found to be higher for boys & urban students, whereas for the dimension interest in using internet mean scores of boys and girls, rural and urban students is found to be nearly the same.

Findings of the study

- The level of internet usage for learning tamil among higher secondary students is low (60.4%).
- Mean score values for all the dimensions are almost nearer to the mid-values of a particular dimension.
- Boys and Girls, Rural and Urban students differ significantly in their internet usage for learning tamil.
- Higher secondary students of Government, Government Aided and Corporation schools as well as from boys, girls, co-education schools differ significantly in their internet usage for learning tamil.
- Mean scores for the dimensions accessibility to internet and awareness is found to be high for boys & urban students whereas for the dimension interest in using internet mean scores of boys and girls, rural and urban students is found to be nearly the same.

Suggestions and Recommendations

- Students should be motivated, encouraged and supported to learn their mother tongue (Tamil), not only for their future career but to know about the literature and the treasure of Tamil language, for the joy of reading and writing.
- Rural and urban gap as far as technology is concerned should be reduced in terms of availability, accessibility and awareness.
- Teachers irrespective of their subject being taught to be technology savvy with right attitude to utilize technology in their teaching process.
- Faculty technology training may be maximized for the integration of pedagogy.
- School authorities should make available the technological learning resources including tamil language laboratory & software to the students as much as

possible along with the technical and supporting staff.

- Incorporating one period in the regular time table for tamil language laboratory.
- Lack of adequate ICT in the class room or failure to properly integrate ICT into the curriculum.
- Technology integration in the language teaching classes is in the implementation phase, but that the change has not become institutionalized.
- To align technology use with the institutional goals of individual schools as the best means of using technology to improve student achievement is not widespread.
- Creating awareness and providing accessibility to the various technological such as blogs ...among the Hr.Sec.Students.

Conclusion

Teachers' role as manager of resources and facilitator of learning need to be emphasized. Learners should be guided and helped by teachers to use technology for language learning (Tamil) in an appropriate way. As rightly pointed out by Delor's Commission "Learning to Learn" is the watchword for today's students of higher secondary level.

Bibliography

- Chinnasamy.K, Sirajunissa Begum S.,(2014). A Study on Usage of Internet resources Among the Engineering Students in Madurai District. *Journal of Modern Science*. Nov, VI.6-No.2.
- John W. Best, James V. Kahn.,(2014). Research in Education., Tenth Edition., PHI Learning Private Limited., New Delhi.
- Mangal.S.K., (2008). Statistics in Psychology and Education. PHI publications, New Delhi.
- Mangal.S.K., (2012). Essentials of Educational Technology, PHI publications, New Delhi.
- Nabel Abedalaziz, Shahrir Jamaluddin, Chin Hai Leng.,(2013). Measuring Attitudes toward computer and internet usage among postgraduate students in Malaysia.

Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology. April, vol 12 Issue 2.

Paul Devanesan.P., Selvan.A.,(2012).Utilization of online programs by Teachers. Edutracks. Nov, Vol.12-No3.

PramodK.Jail, Shamsheer Singh Singh, Prashant Babaji et. al.,(2014). Knowledge and attitude about computer and internet usage among dental students in Western Rajasthan, India. *Journal of International Society of Preventive & Community Dentistry*. Jan-Apr4(1): 29-34.

Radha Mohan., (2013). Innovative Science Teaching. , PHI publications, New Delhi.

Uma Maheswari.K., Samma Reddy.P.,(2010).Assessment of ICT Literacy. Edutracks. Oct,Vol.10-No2.

Venugopal E.P., Santhakumari.K.,(2012).Teaching of Tamil, Saradha publications, Chennai.